

NFDI4Earth

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NFDI4Earth OneStop4All – Release 2

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Executive summary

The OneStop4All is a community portal that serves as the central entry point to NFDI4Earth-developed services and relevant resources for the Earth System Sciences community. In this report, we build upon Deliverables [D4.3.1](#) and [D4.3.4](#), presenting the current structure, key features, and implementation of the OneStop4All, which fulfils the established high-level requirements.

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1 Introduction

The OneStop4All serves a central entry point to key Research Data Management (RDM) resources for the Earth System Sciences (ESS) community, including NFDI4Earth-developed services such as the Knowledge Hub¹, the EduTrain portal², the Living Handbook³, and the User Support Network⁴. Designed through a user-centered approach, the portal has been developed in close collaboration with the community. User needs and feedback were gathered through online and on-site workshops, focusing on aspects such as mockups and content (see Henzen et al. 2023 and Henzen et al. 2024).

The OneStop4All portal is developed incrementally, carried out in close collaboration with various NFDI4Earth measures. The current version (as of March 2025) emphasizes discovery, offering curated information on more than 680,000 datasets, 150 repositories, and 350,000 services - some hosted by NFDI4Earth partners and others by international institutions. Additionally, the portal provides access to open learning resources, tools and software, research data management articles, and standards, aggregated from various sources and managed within the Knowledge Hub.

The current version of the OneStop4All is available at: <https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de/>.

2 Portal Structure

The current portal structure, as illustrated in Fig. 1, provides users with the ability to:

1. Conduct a keyword-based search across all available resources.
2. Explore datasets, repositories, tools, and services, as well as access open educational materials in dedicated portal sections.
3. Gain an overview of available resources, categorized by type.
4. Browse resources individually or refine searches using facet filters based on resource types.
5. Engage with the NFDI4Earth community and contribute to enhancing service content.

¹ <https://knowledgehub.nfdi4earth.de>

² <https://edutrain.nfdi4earth.de>

³ Integrated in the OneStop4All: <https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de/search?resourcetype=Living+Handbook+Article&sort=>

⁴ <https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de/?support>

The portal's modular implementation ensures flexibility and supports future adaptations. We aim to continuously refine and expand sections based on evolving user needs and the growing offerings of NFDI4Earth.

2.1 Discover Datasets and Repositories

Finding relevant datasets and repositories remains a significant challenge in the Earth System Sciences. NFDI4Earth tackles this issue through various initiatives and services, including support for related pilot projects and the User Support Network, which provides personalized assistance in locating relevant resources.

In the OneStop4All, we address this challenge by prominently featuring a dedicated *Datasets & Repositories* section (see Fig. 2). Users can:

- Take a guided tour to refine the list of over 150 repositories through a repository wizard (Fig. 2, left).
- Explore the full collection of curated repositories (Fig. 2, middle).
- Discover Earth System Sciences datasets from a wide range of aggregated sources (Fig. 2, right).

This structured approach simplifies dataset discovery, making it more accessible and user-friendly for the community.

The guided tour helps users filter repositories by answering key questions related to data formats, DOI requirements, and other relevant criteria. These questions are structured around data discovery and data publication, with overlapping aspects such as format and disciplinary focus.

Users can explore repositories through the “Repository Exploration” button, which leads to a curated repository list with various facet filter options. Similarly, the “Dataset Discovery” button provides access to a curated dataset list, featuring advanced filtering options such as spatial and temporal constraints.

To further support data discovery, the OneStop4All portal highlights dataset showcases, featuring openly available and FAIR datasets. Community members can submit dataset showcases by following a short guide (see Fig. 3 “*Suggest your community dataset as a showcase*”) and using a structured template.

Additionally, we present articles on related topics, curated by the Living Handbook team. These articles are requested, reviewed, and/or authored in response to community needs and are displayed in the section below.

Figure 1: Homepage of the OneStop4All portal including keyword search, dedicated areas for most relevant ESS RDM topics, overview of available resources and participation section.

Figure 2: Discover datasets and repositories - section in the OneStop4All portal – including wizard, repository list, and dataset search.

Figure 3: Discover datasets and repositories section in the OneStop4All portal – including highlighted dataset showcases and featured Living Handbook articles.

< Back to starting page

Explore tools and services

Discover semantic resources
Discover relevant resources as linked data from the NFDI4Earth Knowledge Hub service using SPARQL

Discover community tools and software
Find and reuse tools and software to facilitate your Earth System Science data research

Get research data management support
Connect with the NFDI4Earth Helpdesk team to get individual support for your RDM problems

Explore highlighted showcases

Community tool
Lexcube

Community tool
Metbase

Community tool
OSS4Geo

Community tool
Graph-based visual search engine

Community tool
GeoQA Map

Community tool
Galaxy for Earth System

Figure 4: Explore tools and services - including Knowledge Hub access, tools list, and access to the User Support Network.

2.2 Explore Tools and Services

The *Tools & Services* section follows a similar structure to the *Datasets & Repositories* section, ensuring a consistent and user-friendly experience. In its current version, this section provides access to the NFDI4Earth-developed services, including the Knowledge Hub and the User Support Network and a curated list of tools and software (see Fig. 4).

Additionally, we feature tool showcases, highlighting openly available and FAIR tools and relevant Living Handbook articles on related topics.

Looking ahead, we plan to expand this section by introducing curated collections of research data management services and additional pilot showcases, both of which are currently in progress.

2.3 Improve Your Skills and Start Learning

The *Improve your skills and start learning* section offers access to the EduTrain learning portal with interactive learning resources and to a curated list of external open educational resources, collected by Measure 1.3 (Fig. 5).

Below these options, users can explore selected courses, some of which include interactive learning units.

Improve your skills and start learning

Enter the interactive learning portal

Start learning in our NFDI4Earth EduTrain portal to improve your spatial data analysis and management skills

Discover curated community resources

Find open reliable educational resources from sources such as MIT open courseware, EarthLab, and NASA's Earthdata

Start learning with highlighted courses

Course
Python onboarding

Course
How to create publishable netcdf-data

Course
Image processing

Course
Python for spatial data analysis

Course
Understanding data chunking

Figure 5: Improve your skills and start learning – including access to the EduTrain learning portal and external learning materials as well as featured courses.

Attend virtual or on-site training events

Training event
Legal Workshop Series April 2025 – April 2026 (virtual, open events)

Training event
Winter School on RDM 18th – 20th March 2025 (Cologne, 2nd cohort event)

Training event
Coffee Lectures October 2024 – March 2025 (virtual, open events)

Training event
Workshop DataCubes 28th – 29th August 2024 (virtual, Academy event)

Training event
Cross-Community Hackathon 23rd – 5th December 2023 (open event)

Learn more about education and training

Article
What is the NFDI4Earth Academy

Article
Explore the Academy and connect with peers

Article
Suggest your learning material

Figure 6: Improve your skills and start learning – including NFDI4Earth Academy information and events.

The NFDI4Earth Academy hosts online coffee lectures on relevant RDM topics, services, and activities, as well as additional free on-site and online events. The OneStop4All provides up-to-date information about the NFDI4Earth Academy and these events as Living Handbook articles (Fig. 6).

3 Implementation Details

The source code is published on GitLab under the Apache 2.0 License and managed in several sub projects:

<https://git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi4earth/onestop4all>

The main functionality and sections' structure are implemented in React, based on the [Open Pioneer Trails](#) framework, organised in the implementation project:

<https://git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi4earth/onestop4all/onestop4all-implementation>

Articles are managed as Markdown documents in the Living Handbook GitLab project, which is organised by the Living Handbook team:

<https://git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi4earth/livinghandbook>

This approach enables article content to be updated without modifying the OneStop4All source code. Articles and their related metadata are harvested through the Knowledge Hub and seamlessly integrated into the OneStop4All, where they are rendered alongside BibTeX sources and the Living Handbook outline.

The OneStop4All GitLab projects are also used to organise the sprints, document the implementation schedule and collect feature requests (see Henzen et al. 2024).

Information about the OneStop4All as an NFDI4Earth-developed service and integral part of the NFDI4Earth Software Architecture:

<https://nfdi4earth.pages.rwth-aachen.de/architecture/architecture-docs>

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